

25 000 cm^{-1} in the reflectance spectra of Cu(SMPT) arise from a combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g} + {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively in a tetragonal field⁶.

In 3μ region the ligand displays medium and broad bands at 3 290 and 3 090 cm^{-1} assignable to OH and CH stretches. The complexes display only one band at $3\,040 \pm 60 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, but in aquo-complexes a broad band is observed at $3\,450\text{--}3\,050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The free ligand displays a weak and broad band at $2\,758 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to SH+hydrogen bonded OH stretches. In complexes, the SH stretches disappear suggesting coordination of thiol sulphur on deprotonation. In the region $1\,620\text{--}1\,237 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the ligand displays a number of bands at 1 620, 1 610, 1 575, 1 533, 1 495, 1 485, 1 423, 1 373, 1 295 and $1\,237 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to phenyl and triazole ring skeletal vibrations. The ir band at $1\,620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to aldimino $\nu_{C=N}$ shifted to lower frequency by 5–30 cm^{-1} indicating the involvement of C=N nitrogen in coordination. A strong band at $1\,575 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in ir spectrum of the ligand is assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$ vibrations of triazole ring. The band shifted to higher frequency in almost all the complexes. The blue-shift of $\nu_{C=N}$ band indicates the bonding of C=N nitrogen with the metal atom¹¹. The ir band at $1\,533 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to thioamide band-I¹²⁻¹⁴. As expected this band shifted to higher wave number and merge together with other C=N stretch and observed near $1\,590\text{--}1\,615 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The thioamide band-II ($1\,237 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) also shifted to higher wave number and was observed near $1\,248 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The thioamide band-III ($1\,035 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was observed as a very weak band near $1\,067 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. The shifting of thioamide band I, II and III to higher wave numbers indicates the involvement of thioamide group in coordination. The thioamide band-IV (754 cm^{-1}) also moved to lower frequencies and was observed near $705 \pm 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to coordination of thioamide sulphur in these complexes. A broad band at $1\,373 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ of free ligand which disappeared in the complexes was assigned to δ_{OH} . A medium band at $1\,130 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ir spectra of the free ligand was assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ (phenolic) vibration. In complexes the $\nu_{C=O}$ shifted to $1\,403 \pm 18 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that double bond character of CO has increased, as usually observed in the complexes^{11,12} with bridged phenolic oxygen. A medium band near $848 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in aquo-copper(II) and -nickel(II) complexes indicated the involvement of water molecules in coordination¹⁵. The ligand displayed a number of bands in the range $690\text{--}450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which were assigned to ring deformation vibrations. In the complexes these are affected slightly due to drainage of electron density towards metal ions on coordination.

Thus from infrared spectral studies it is inferred that the ligand is bonded through deprotonated thiol sulphur, phenolic oxygen, and aldimino C=N nitrogen.

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Manganese(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with Cytosine

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Manuscript received 11 August 1988, revised 2 March 1989,
accepted 25 April 1989

CYTOSINE possesses four different potential metal binding sites as indicated by asterisk in 1. Though some reports^{1,2} are available in the literature where cytosine acts as a bidentate ligand, very few reports³ of cytosine acting as a monodentate ligand are available. The crystal structure of three metal complexes of cytosine have been reported¹ and all three are copper(II) complexes containing neutral cytosine ligand coordinating through the N(3) position of the ring and an axial intramolecular Cu...O(2) interaction. In 2:1 cytosine-CaCl₂ and in 1:1 cytosine-CaCl₂ adducts cytosine is found to act as chelating ligand coordinating through its N(3) and C(2)=O. The tetrahedral complex CoL₄(ClO₄)₂, where L=cytosine, contains

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a monodentate coordination of cytosine through its N(3). As the N(1) position of cytosine is attached to ribose in a nucleoside or a ribose

phosphate in a nucleotide, the attachment of metal ions to this position is of marginal biological interest⁴. In this paper we report the isolation and characterisation of some new complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with cytosine acting as a monodentate ligand through its N(3).

Experimental

Cytosine was obtained from Sigma, and other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of complexes: Respective metal chloride salt (except in the case of iron, where, FeSO₄·7H₂O was used under nitrogen atmosphere) dissolved in aqueous ethanol was added to a solution of cytosine in boiling aqueous ethanol (metal-cytosine ratio 1:2). pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.5 by adding 0.1 N NaOH and refluxed for 12 h and then cooled to room temperature. The resulting coloured crystalline complex was washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl₂. The metal and nitrogen were estimated⁵. Carbon and hydrogen were analysed from Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

The complexes were characterised on the basis of elemental analysis (Table 1), conductance, magnetic, ir and uv spectral data. Thermogravimetric analysis was also performed.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	μ _{eff} B.M.	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)	
			M	N
[MnL ₄]Cl ₂	Light grey	5.93	9.53 (9.63)	29.45 (29.47)
[FeL ₄]SO ₄	Brown	4.95	9.36 (9.37)	28.20 (28.19)
[CoL ₄]Cl ₂	Reddish violet	4.27	10.27 (10.26)	29.25 (29.27)
[NiL ₄]Cl ₂	Green	3.26	10.20 (10.23)	29.27 (29.28)
[CuL ₄]Cl ₂	Blue	1.89	10.97 (10.98)	30.98 (29.03)

*L=Cytosine.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are coloured, solid and quite stable in air. All the complexes are soluble in water and other polar solvents like methanol, but insoluble in non-polar solvents like CCl₄. On the basis of their analytical data complexes may be formulated as [ML₄]X₂. The molar conductance values of the complexes in water (10⁻³ M) lie in the range 190–220 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicating them as 2:1 electrolyte⁶. The chloride anions can be quantitatively precipitated out from the aqueous solutions of the chloro-complexes indicating their presence in the secondary coordination sphere.

TGA curves indicate that the complexes start decomposing around 230° and on increasing temperature they decompose without forming any stable intermediates.

The solid state electronic spectra of the Fe^{II} complex exhibit a very strong broad band in the near-infrared region at 4 350 cm⁻¹ due to ⁵T_{2g}←⁵E_g transition which is typical of tetrahedral Fe^{II} complex⁷. The Co^{II} complex exhibits a weak absorption broad split band in the near-infrared region at 6 800 cm⁻¹ and a very strong split band in the visible region at 14 800 cm⁻¹, corresponding to transitions ⁴T_{1g}(F)←⁴A_{1g}(ν₃) and ⁴T_{1g}(P)←⁴A_{1g}(ν₃). Theoretical calculations for the value of ν₁ with the experimental values of ν₂ and ν₃ is found to be 3 024 cm⁻¹ and the value of Δ is found to be 3 780 cm⁻¹ indicating the tetrahedral stereochemistry of the Co^{II} complex⁸. The Ni^{II} complex exhibits a weak absorption band at 7 100 cm⁻¹ due to ³A_{2g}←³T_{1g} transition (ν₂) and another strong band at 14 100 cm⁻¹ due to ³T_{1g}(P)←³T_{1g} transition (ν₃). The value of ν₁ is calculated theoretically with these experimental values of ν₂ and ν₃ and is found to be 3 945 cm⁻¹. The value of Δ is also 3 945 cm⁻¹ which is characteristic for tetrahedral complex⁹. The Cu^{II} complex shows a strong broad band at 14 200 cm⁻¹ indicating its square-planar geometry⁹. The magnetic moment values (Table 1) also support the monomeric tetrahedral stereochemistries for the Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes and square-planar geometry for the Cu^{II} complex¹⁰.

All the complexes exhibit more or less similar infrared spectral pattern. The absorption bands of the complexes were compared to that of the free cytosine as given in the literature¹¹. Our main interest is in the range 1 700–800 cm⁻¹ where NH, CO, CH and CN vibrations occur. Since the frequencies at 1 540 and 825 cm⁻¹ due to N(1)-H out-of-plane and in-plane vibrations of cytosine remain unchanged both in position and intensity in the complexes, it can be proposed that N(1) site of cytosine is not involved in coordination. If N(3) position of cytosine acts as a donor then it will assume slightly positive charge and due to inductive and mesomeric effects there will be change in C-NH and C-N frequencies¹². Also the C=N+C=C frequency will be changed due to the redistribution of π-electrons in the conjugated C=C, C=N and C=O systems of the cytosine ring¹². Also the migration of electrons from N(3) position to C(2)=O will be changed affecting the C=O frequency. In the complexes, the C-NH₂+C-N ring stretching frequency at 1 290 cm⁻¹ of cytosine¹² shifted to higher frequency and their intensity greatly reduced. Also the shoulder at 1 600 cm⁻¹ and the strong band at 1 503 cm⁻¹ in cytosine¹² due to C=N+C=C stretching frequencies shifted to higher frequencies in the complexes. The ν_{C=O} at 1 645 cm⁻¹ in cytosine also shifted to higher frequency. All these indicate that cytosine coordinates to the metal through its N(3).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the University of Kalyani for providing a fellowship to one of them (R. K. B).

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Short Synthesis of (Z)-7-Heneicosene and (Z)-7-Tricosene

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Manuscript received 31 October 1988, accepted 31 March 1989

RECENTLY it has been found that (Z)-7-heneicosene (1) and (Z)-7-tricosene (2) are the pheromone components of *A. eurtula*^{1,2}. The strategy for the construction of 1 and 2 is depicted in Scheme 1. The reaction sequence involves the preparation of 4-undecyn-1-ol (3) by reacting tetra-

hydrofurfuryl chloride with n-hexyl bromide in presence of lithium amide in liquid ammonia³. Partial hydrogenation of acetylenic bond in 3 using Lindlar's catalyst in presence of quinoline yielded (Z)-4-undecenol (4) in 90% yield. Bromination of 4 with PBr₃/Py in anhydrous ether gave 1-bromo-(Z)-4-undecene (5) the Grignard of which was then coupled⁴ with decyl bromide and dodecyl bromide in presence of catalytic amount of Li₂CuCl₄ at -10° in anhydrous THF as solvent. The purification of the coupled product using silica gel (200-100 mesh; Acme) afforded (Z)-7-heneicosene (1) and (Z)-7-tricosene (2) respectively in 60% yield.

Experimental

The compounds were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (200-100 mesh; Acme) and thin layer chromatography using silica gel G (NCL, Poona). The purity was confirmed by elemental analysis from Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Panjab University, Chandigarh. Ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal reference. The organic extracts were dried over Na₂SO₄. The air and moisture sensitive reactions were carried out under N₂ atmosphere.

4-Undecyn-1-ol (3): Tetrahydrofurfuryl chloride (12.0 g, 0.1 mol) was added to a stirred solution of lithium amide (0.3 mol; prepared from 2.1 g Li metal) in liquid ammonia during 15 min. After 3 h stirring, 1-bromohexane (16.5 g, 0.1 mol) dissolved in dry THF was added during 30 min. The reaction mixture was then quenched with saturated solution of NH₄Cl after 3 h stirring and the residue extracted in ether. The solvent was evaporated and subsequent column chromatography afforded 3 (10.08 g, 60%) (Found: C, 78.42; H, 11.78. C₁₁H₂₀O requires: C, 78.57; H, 11.90%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3 600-3 500 (OH) and 2 210 cm⁻¹ (acetylenic); δ (CCl₄) 3.6 (3H, m, CH₂OH), 2.1

